

NIKOLAY BERDYAEV EXISTENTIALISM

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Abstract: This article briefly covers the humanitarian ideas of Nikolay Berdyaev, one of the great representatives of the existentialist philosophy. The article shows that the issue of art occupies a central place in the existentialism of Nikolay Berdyaev.

Key words: existentialism, humanism, alienation, absurdity, rebellion, revolution, art, beauty, freedom, human rights, meaning of life.

Аннотация: В статье кратко рассматриваются гуманитарные идеи Николая Бердяева, одного из крупнейших представителей экзистенциалистской философии. В статье показано, что проблема искусства занимает центральное место в экзистенциализме Николая Бердяева.

Ключевые слова: экзистенциализм, гуманизм, отчуждение, абсурд, бунт, революция, искусство, красота, свобода, права человека, смысл жизни.

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада экзистенциализм фалсафасининг йирик вакилларида бири Николай Бердяевнинг инсонпарварлик ғоялари қисқача ёритилган. Мақолада Николай Бердяев экзистенциализмида санъат масаласи асосий ўрин тутиши кўрсатиб ўтилган.

Калит сўзлар: экзистенциализм, гуманизм, бегоналашиш, бемаънилиқ, исён, инқилоб, санъат, гўзаллик, эркинлик, инсон ҳуқуқлари, ҳаётнинг маъноси.

N.A. Berdyaev (1874-1948) is a Russian philosopher who represented existentialism.

Buduchi existentialist, Berdyaev provodit seryoznoe razlichie mejdu bytiem i sushchestvovaniem. Pri etom subject interpretiruet sushchestvovanie kak dushu. Po ego mneniyu, existence-sut ne sushchestvuet v reality, a sushchestvuet lish v protivopolojnost dukhovnomu sushchestvovaniyu. Only the subjective soul has real existence. Po vzglyadam Berdyaeva, bytie raskryvaetsya through the subject, a sodержanie emu pridaetsya sub'ektom.

Berdyaev schitaet filosofiyu poznaniem mira iznutri cherez dukhovnyi mir lichnosti. A nauka, po mysli myslitelya, poznaet mir izvne, to est vne cheloveka. Berdyaev pokazyvaet, chto tsel filosofskogo poznaniya sostoit ne v

vospriyatii deystvitelnosti, a v zamechanii ee soderjaniya. On myslit analogously to the rule of Socrates: "Poznay samogo sebya, i cherez nego ty poznaesh mir" [1:28]. Sam Berdyaev admits that the "human problem" is in the center of ego philosophy, i poetomu v ego uchenii ponimanie mirozdaniya i tochnoe reshenie chelovecheskoy problemy idut ruka ob ruku.

Berdyaev schitaet, chto sushchestvuet tri tipa vremeni. Pervyy kosmicheski-vechen i opisan v krugе vichrya; vtoroy, istorichesky, kotoryy predstavlen liniey, soedinyayushchey proshloe s budushchim; the third is existential, which is defined as a tochkoй, soobshchayushchey vnutrennee dvijenie shower. Ekzistentsialnoe vremya, po Berdyaevu, ne yavlyaetsya sostoyaniem razvitiya vneshnego mira, a napravleno na opisanie Mira Vysshego i oznachaet glubokoe proniknovenie dushi v sebya. Svoboda pervichna ne v istoricheskom smysle, a v eksistentsialnyx vremennyx koordinax, to est s toчки zreniya lichnosti. Kajetsya, chto svoboda podobna bezdne, "bespochvennoy osnoe sushchestvovaniya". On pervichnee Boga, a takje prejde sushchestvovaniya. "Primat svobody nad sushchestvovaniem" is the first rule of philosophy. S odnoy storony, svoboda est nichto, a s secondoy storony, eto volya, nichem ne obuslovlennaya tvorcheskaya sila, besporyadochnaya volevaya sila po otnosheniyu k chemu-libo.

Bog tvorit i proyavlyaet sebya iz nebytiya. A garden is a subject. Berdyaeva's concept of God is more filosof, chem religioznaya, to est proniknutaya filosofskim soderjaniem. Bog ne yavlyaetsya ni prichinoy Vselennoy, ni siloy v estestvennom smysle. On ne yavlyaetsya ni regulyatorom vselennoy, ni absolyutnym pravitelem. Bog ne pravit chelovekom i vselennoy. Vselennaya i chelovek byli zozdany Bogom, no v to je vremya oni byli otdeleny ot Boga. The garden is a higher spirit, "substance and truth of the Universe" - a special personality, not a suschnost, a suschestvovanie. Berdyaev firmly stands for nature and dualism, necessity and freedom. To est on dumal o mirakh, sovershenno otlichayushchixsya drug ot druga. S odnoy storony, est mir dukhovnyy i svobodnyy, s secondoy — mir estestvennyy i neobhodimyy. Berdyaev approached Bogu kak k "vysshey forme sushchestvovaniya" in the early period of his creativity, and in the last period of his creativity, he used the concepts of suschestvovaniya and ponimanii Boga. Po otnosheniyu k chelovecheskoy lichnosti Bog ne suschestvuet v obektivnoy forme, kak nechto neshnee. Bog vseгда v lichnosti i svobode i nikogda v estestvennom mire i neobhodimosti. Ono napravleno na svobodu cheloveka i ne prinujdaet cheloveka ispovedovatsya. Vera v Boga — eto lish vnutrennyaya vstrecha v dukhovnom

opyte. Poetomu Berdyaev schitaet, chto obretnenie chelovekom svyashchenstva i stremlenie k Pervosvyashchenstvu yavlyayetsya edinsennym svidetelstvom sushchestvovaniya Boga.

Vopreki dualizmu dvukh mirov, kotoryy on reshitelno zashchishchal, Berdyaev utverjdaet takje, chto dukhovnoe nachalo prevoskhodit suschestvovanie, rukovodstvo Dukha viditsya v sozdanii obraza sushchestvovaniya. To est eto vidno v sodержanii suschestvuyushchikh sobytij.

Miroponimanie Berdyaeva priobretaet pluralisticheskiy character. Razdeleniya ne sushchestvuet, sushchestvovanie sostoit iz sushchnostey. Kajdaya individualnost yavlyayetsya sushchnostyu. Pluralism proyavlyayetsya i v tsarstve dukha. Khotya Berdyaev mnogo ispolzuet ponyatie dushi, on govorit o "lichnyx dushakh", to est o bozhestvennyx i chelovecheskix dushakh. Tolko oni yavlyayutsya sub'ektami i "existential centers". Poetomu govoryat, chto existentialism Berdyaeva has a personalistic character. Everyone has the ability to be free and creative. Dukhi prevoskhodyat prirodu. Vysshee sobytie ne mojet vzniknut snizu. Dushi-sub'ekty sozdayut nerealnye i voobrajaemye sushchestva, predmety. The object depends on the subject, poskolku blagodarya subject object imeet smysl i sodержanie. B zavisimosti ot sostoyaniya subject object mojet menyatsya. Vneshniy mir sostoit iz sovokupnosti manifestation i znakov vnutrennego mira, all processes, izkhodyashchie v subjective mire, ne proyavlyayutsya yarko v ektivnym mire. Yavleniya mira, v kotorom my jivem, yavlyayutsya lish priznakami sub'ektivnogo mira. Blagodarya subjectivenomu miru i izmeneniyam v nem vznikayet mir "ob'ektivatsii", to est mir "subchineniya", "utraty svobody".

Objectification — odno iz tsentralnyx ponyatij filosofii Berdyaeva. Objectification is close to the concept of "extermination" and causes evil. Po mneniyu filosofa, istochnikom zla vo vneshnem mire yavlyayetsya protest protiv ob'ektivatsii etogo mira. Dusha ne otkryvaetsya v predmentax, a zakryvaetsya, proyavlyayetsya izmenennoy. Man popadaet v chujduyu emu mirskuyu sredu, on horse. Cheloveku kajetsya, chto subject emu ne prinadlejit. Poetomu on bolshe vnimania udelyaet materialnosti, chem veshney nekhodimostimosti. Lyudi stanovyatsya rabami objects. Koren vsech chelovecheskix stradaniy — mir obektov.

B rezuleta otchujdeniya ot Boga, t. e. otchujdeniya cheloveka ot samogo sebya, nad nim nachinayut gospodstvovat neokhodimost i materialnost. Ono razrushayet tvorcheskij entuziazm human, gubit ego. The same person preserves the ability to create and sustain destruction. Berdyaev nerazryvno soedinyayet

ponyatiya Boga i cheloveka. The relationship between a person and God is not natural, but a spiritual-existential character.

Kak prizyv k prevoskhodstvu, Bog raskryvaetsya v cheloveke, a chelovek raskryvaetsya v Boge. Sledovatelno, Vsevyshniy, istinnaya chelovechnost, bozhestvenna. Berdyaev otvergaet principle samosushchestvovaniya Boga, nezavisimogo ot cheloveka, kak "formu idolopoklonstva". Poetomu, po vzglyadam Berdyaeva, glavnyaya problema filosofii ne Bog, a Bog est chelovek i Bog est chelovechestvo. However, according to ego mneniyu, a person has two ideals - bozhestvennomu (spiritual, existential) and natural (material, necessary, good). Vot pochemu chelovek nakhoditsya v protivorechii. It unites Vysshee and nizshee, svobodu and svobodu, v kotoroy iseghodit borba mejdu Bogom i mirom.

Berdyaev predstavlyal cheloveka kak slojnyuyu edinitsu lichnosti i lichnosti. Humanity is a natural-biological phenomenon, subordinate to both natural and social necessity. A person is a "creative energetic center", a moral-spiritual development, the milk of which is freedom and creativity, which is created in this world in the image of an "isklyuchitelnyy".

Berdyaev understands, chto chelovek zanimaet tsentralnoe mesto v prirode. Eto iskhodit iz dukhovnykh aspektov lyudey. Poskolku chelovek yavlyaetsya nositelem i hozyainom sushchnosti sushchestvovaniya, Vselennaya yavlyaetsya chastyu cheloveka, a ne naoborot. Every human being is a microcosm and a microtheos, and the heart of a human being comes from history and society. Dumat, chto chelovek — nichto pered Bogom ili chto on simple instrument — ne chto inoe, kak unigenie, na samom dele chelovek nezavisim. Potomu chto svoboda i tvorchestvo, sushchestvuyushchie v nem, ne tolko ot Boga, no i ot svobody bytiya. Svoboda sama po sebe yavlyaetsya istochnikom kak zla, tak i dobra. Bog ne hochet razrushat svobodu i lish prizyvaet cheloveka tvorit dobro. However, people should freely choose between good and evil. Po suti, chelovek ne stanovitsya polnostyu zrelym samostoyatelno. On preodolevaet razlichnyye prepyatstviya na puti k dostizheniyu takikh cennostey "vysshey jizni", kak dukhovnaya nezavisimost, dobro, ljubov, istina i krasota. В этом смысле человек - это не готовое существование, это холмовеческий идеал. A human being is a human being.

Berdyaev fly, chto k cheloveku i lichnosti neokhodimo podhodit s personalisticheskoy tochki zreniya. He considers that a good person is a concrete, individual existence, a separate existential center, a controlling force that creates spiritual wealth. Dukhovnye tsennosti, fortune ne budut suschestvovat kak zamorogennaya, obektivnaya, obshchaya informatsiya. It can

be adjusted individually. The philosopher obyasnayet tak his personalism: Bojestvennost proyavlyaetsya only in individual, not in collective, not in general. Berdyaev did not recognize the rule of prevoskhodstva vida nad lichnostyu, natsii, gosudarstva i obshchestva nad lichnostyu. Myslitel, schitavshiy, chto "human lichnost is unique, non-repetitive, independent, high value" [2:228].

Kak philosopher Berdyaev socentrochil vnimanie na otnosheniakh meжду lichnostyu i suschestvom. On nazyval pridrou i obshchestvo osnonoy formoy sushchestvovaniya i ob'ektivatsii. Gosudarstvo, vlast, obshchestvennye orderki, "mechanicheskoe" soobshchestvo lyudey gasyat "Tsarstvo Dukha".

Human resources - technology, economics, etc. rassmatrivayutsya kak ego tsel, lyudi perestayut zadumyvatsya o smysle jizni. Sotsialnaya istoriya delaet cheloveka svoim orujem, dushit ego svobodu. And etom mire lichnost nakhoditsya v sostoyanii postoyannogo i nerazreshimogo konflikta s obshchestvom. Voorujennyi svoim vnutrennim Ya, stremleniem k svobode, lichnost soprotivlyaetsya vneshnemu davleniyu obshchestva. В результате неприятия мира цивилизации человек наполняется страхом, грустью и надеждой. Но, в том же протисе духовных истязаний, человек получает заповед Божию, он стremitsya k svetu i dobru.

Glavnaya zadacha obshchestva, govorit Berdyaev, – spasti chelovechestvo. Eto dostigaetsya putem vozvrashcheniya k bojestvennosti, vossoedineniya s procesom oboreniya. Blagodarya sovместному deystviyu Boga i cheloveka objectification prekrashchaetsya. Human creativity should have a decisive role in the process. True creation means the emergence of something new, something that is not in doubt in the Universe. Poetomu tvorchestvo - eto preodolenie sushchestvuyushchey reality, proryv iz nebytiya na novyy uroven sushchestvovaniya, k novomu sodержaniyu. Tvorenie ne mojet suschestvovat bez materii. No ono opredelyaetsya svobodoy, kotoraya sozdaet innovatsii i podchinyaet materialnoe duhu. Tvorchestvo trebuet subject. The subject of creation is a person. Po ego mneniyu, lichnost est "tvorcheskoe yavlenie, deyatelnost, soprotivlenie, pobeda nad silami mira, prazdnovanie pobedy nad mirovym rabstvom, bunt cheloveka protiv rabstva" [2: 14-56].

Berdyaev schital, chto prednaznachenie i zadacha cheloveka - sozdavat dukhovnye cennosti. Odnako v usloviyakh sivilizatsii individuale tvorchestvo ne mojet prinesti lyudyam polnuyu svobodu. The result of individual creation - cultural sobytie - subject to objectification, and in the result of this culture prinimaet antichelovecheskoe napravlenie.

Berdyayev believes that the meaning of history is the quality of the form of alienation of a person from society. The completion of history, ideally, means the end of objectification. That is, it means that a person will be free from alienation, enmity, impersonality. The philosopher equates the end of history and its objectification with a "real revolution of the soul". Berdyayev viewed the social revolution as a destructive force. He had a negative attitude to the socialist experiment in Russia. He considered it a new way of oppressing people and ensuring social injustice. The spiritual revolution raised by the thinker, in his opinion, does not mean the destruction and denial of worldly and social existence, but rather, it means clarifying them with the spirit. That is, it means to completely creatively change the universe. In this, existential time wins over cosmic and historical time, the contradiction between subject and object disappears, and a person becomes free from this world and achieves inner freedom. A "higher consciousness" appears in people and they accept other levels of values where spirituality takes the highest place. The reign of God-humanity begins. God will win.

According to Berdyayev, the next version of the completion of history will be inappropriate, bad. If people direct their creativity in the direction of evil, cosmic and social destruction will occur.

Thus, Berdyayev, contrary to consistent Orthodox theology, asserts that the divine kingdom means not only the washing away of sins and the restoration of people to their original state of purity, but also the creation of a new world by them. In order to introduce such a world, a heavy, serious struggle will be necessary, which will require losses and sufferings, and will show the activity of the entire creative force [3: 284-285]. Only at the end of history, man can enter the "new zone" of existence. Man is a participant in the divine creation, and therefore participated in the creation of the world together with God. The history of society is controlled by three forces - God, historical necessity and man. Humans play the main role in these.

Berdyayev considers both capitalism and communism to be undesirable social systems. According to him, the emerging society will be a Christian "personal socialism" in which the supremacy of the individual over the society is ensured. In such a society, each person is recognized as an absolute value and increases in value as a being, which is attracted to eternity. In such a society, social organizations would have created opportunities for everyone to live a fulfilling life. In personalistic socialism, according to Berdyayev, there can be a world of deep spiritual-spiritual communication between people.

In such a society, the internal spiritual community of people - the Cathedral is formed. It is not necessary for individuals to unite as a spiritual unit. Because collectivity itself is a manifestation of the rule of existence that is beyond man. In this case, free spirits will be in a state of "federalism of spirits".

Berdyayev fought for the spiritual and social emancipation of a person who is inextricably linked to each other. Among the philosophers of the 20th century, he is the most consistent and firm thinker in the view that each individual is a value in itself. A philosopher who stated that it is impossible to allow the masses to rule over the human individual. He writes: "Not only a genius, but any person is superior to society and the state, and likewise the true human interest is superior to the interests of society and the state" [4:67]. Berdyayev believes that it is necessary not to allow a person to be sacrificed for the sake of some form of social order and idea. Treating a person as a supreme value should be based on the recognition of the absolute nature of human rights. In this, Berdyayev objects to the supporters of natural rights, who claim that human rights are rooted in their natural foundations. Apart from the alienation of human rights, the philosopher sees the methodological basis in something else, that is, in the supremacy of people over nature, in the freedom and spirituality of the individual, in the likeness of each individual person to God. On this basis, Berdyayev strongly opposed the death penalty.

Berdyayev's philosophy is imbued with deep humanism, which shows that the fate of the world can be decided by liberating each person. Berdyayev's ideas encourage a person to strive, to form and develop himself and the world. That is why Berdyayev's teaching still has its admirers and has not lost its importance.

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